

ROLE OF NEUTROPHIL-LYMPHOCYTE RATIO AS AN ASSESSMENT TOOL OF GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN DIABETIC PATIENTS

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Abstract

Objective:

To compare the mean NLR levels in diabetic patients who maintain good glycemic control versus those with poor control.

Methods:

In this cross-sectional study, we included 100 patients with diabetes who had a duration of at least 12 months from the diabetes control unit of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. Patients having HbA1c levels. <7% were labelled as having good control (Group I), while those having HbA1c \geq 7% were labelled as having poor glycemic control (Group II). The neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) was determined for each patient.

Results:

The mean age of patients was 51.7 (\pm 11.2) years. Regarding gender, 72 (72.0%) were male and 28 (28%) were female. Regarding glycemic control, 24 individuals (24.0%) had good control, whereas a significant majority of 76 individuals (76.0%) had poor glycemic control. Patients with good glycemic control had a mean NLR of 2.00 (SD 0.41), while those with poor control had a mean NLR of 3.26 (SD 0.72) (P-value <0.0001).

Conclusion:

NLR is significantly associated with poor glycemic control in diabetic patients. So NLR can be used as an alternative tool for diabetes monitoring specially in facilities where there is lack of HbA1c testing.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes has emerged as a significant global health challenge, contributing to high rates of illness, disability, and death. It is projected to be the eighth leading cause of both death and disability worldwide.¹ By 2021, approximately 529 million individuals of all ages were living with diabetes across the globe. The age-standardized prevalence rate for diabetes was 6.1%, reflecting a substantial increase of 90.5% since 1990, when it was 3.2%. Predictions indicate that this prevalence could rise to 9.8%, potentially affecting around 1.31 billion people. It is

important to highlight that Type 2 Diabetes (T2D) constitutes over 96% of all cases. In 2021, the prevalence of diabetes was higher among males than females, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.14, although this ratio varied across different regions.^{2,3}

Chronic low-level inflammation plays a significant role in the development of Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), primarily by contributing to insulin resistance. Persistent inflammation is also involved in the onset of both microvascular and macrovascular complications associated with the

disease.⁴ The HbA1c test, which analyzes blood samples, provides an average of blood glucose levels over a three-month period and is a vital tool for managing diabetes. Elevated HbA1c levels are generally linked to worse health outcomes. This test remains a standard method for tracking the effectiveness of treatments for both Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes.⁵ However, it is important to note that the HbA1c measurement does not reveal underlying inflammatory processes that may be present.

Recently, the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has gained recognition as a reliable marker of systemic inflammation across a range of health conditions. It serves as an effective biomarker for detecting low-grade inflammatory processes present in disorders such as metabolic syndrome, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus.^{6, 7} Neutrophils, which constitute the predominant type of white blood cells in the bloodstream, are quick to respond to inflammatory signals, resulting in elevated neutrophil counts during inflammatory episodes. Moreover, these inflammatory triggers can elevate cytokine levels, which promote neutrophilia (increase in neutrophils) and lymphopenia (decrease in lymphocytes). As a result, the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes—known as the NLR—provides a valuable indicator of the inflammatory state within the body.⁸ The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has been identified as a significant independent factor in predicting serious outcomes such as death, complications, and overall long-term prognosis. Additionally, NLR serves as a valuable instrument for population screening, early disease detection, and evaluating the effectiveness of treatments.^{9, 10}

Recent research has extensively explored the relationship between the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and diabetes mellitus (DM), establishing a significant association and correlation. As a result, this area remains a focal point of ongoing investigation. The primary objective of this study was to compare the average NLR levels in diabetic patients who maintain good glycemic control versus those with poor control.

METHODS:

In this cross-sectional study, we included 100 patients with diabetes who had a duration of at least 12 months from the diabetes control unit of Holy

Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. While febrile patients, pregnant women, those on medications that affect leukocyte count like methotrexate, phenytoin, olanzapine, etc., or patients with any history of medical or hematological illness were excluded.

Demographic information, including age, gender, and baseline information regarding BMI, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c%, was documented on the designed protocol. Based on HbA1c%, patients were divided into two groups: patients having HbA1c <7% were labelled as having good control (Group I), while those having HbA1c \geq 7% were labelled as having poor glycemic control (Group II).

Blood samples from each patient were obtained with aseptic measures and stored in vials containing EDTA. Differential leukocyte count (DLC) was done on peripheral smears to obtain the neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR).

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. An independent t-test was used to compare NLR between the two groups, taking p-value <0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

The baseline characteristics of the study population revealed a mean age of 51.7 (\pm 11.2) years. The average body mass index (BMI) was 27.6 (\pm 3.2) kg/m². Regarding gender, 72 (72.0%) were male and 28 (28.0%) were female. In terms of educational status, 15 (15.0%) individuals were illiterate, 85 (85.0%) had received school education or higher education. The residence of the participants was predominantly urban, with 62 (62.0%) individuals, compared to 38 (38.0%) were living in rural areas. Regarding socioeconomic status, 22 individuals (22.0%) belonged to the upper class, 52 individuals (52.0%) fell into the middle class, and 26 individuals (26.0%) were classified as lower class. Glycemic control assessments indicated that 24 individuals (24.0%) had good control, whereas a significant majority of 76 individuals (76.0%) had poor glycemic control (Table 1).

Patients with good glycemic control had a mean NLR of 2.00 (SD 0.41), while those with poor control had a mean NLR of 3.26 (SD 0.72). The analysis revealed a significant difference (P-value <0.0001), indicating a strong association between glycemic control and NLR levels (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age (Y)	51.7 ± 11.2
BMI (Kg/m ²)	27.6 ± 3.2
Gender (%)	
Male	72 (72.0%)
Female	28 (28.0%)
Educational Status (%)	
Illiterate	15 (15.0%)
School education or above	85 (85.0%)
Residence (%)	
Urban	62 (62.0%)
Rural	38 (38.0%)
Socioeconomic Status (%)	
Upper	22 (22.0%)
Middle	52 (52.0%)
Lower	26 (26.0%)
Glycemic Control (%)	
Good	24 (24.0%)
Poor	76 (76.0%)

Table 2. Comparison of NLR in patients with Good versus Poor Glycemic Control.

NLR	Glycemic Control		P-value
	Good Control (N=74)	Poor Control (N=226)	
Mean	2.0	3.26	<0.0001
S.D.	0.41	0.72	

DISCUSSION:

Managing patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is crucial to prevent long-term health complications. T2DM is associated with an increased risk of both infectious and non-infectious conditions, including invasive fungal infections, chronic kidney disease, and cardiovascular disorders.^{11, 12} Traditionally, diagnosis and management rely on biomarkers such as fasting blood glucose levels and HbA1c measurements.¹³ However, recent studies suggest that the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) might serve as a useful predictor of disease severity in individuals with T2DM, offering a potential tool for better disease monitoring and management.^{10, 14}

In this study, we find a significant association of NLR with glycemic control in T2DM patients; the mean NLR was 2.0±0.41 in patients with good glycemic control and 3.26±0.72 in patients with poor glycemic control. Similar results were reported by

Liaquat et al. who reported mean NLR of 2.7±1.0 in patients with good glycemic control and 4.3±2.80 in patients with poor glycemic control.¹⁵

Consistent with prior research, this study demonstrates that the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) can serve as an additional indicator of glycemic control in patients with T2DM, alongside the traditional HbA1c measurement.^{16, 17} The NLR reflects the detrimental impact of neutrophils on vascular endothelial integrity and highlights the protective, antiatherosclerotic function of lymphocytes.¹⁸ In T2DM, persistent low-grade inflammation involves the accumulation of white blood cells in the vascular tissues, driven by oxidative stress and the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines.¹⁹ The utility of NLR as an inflammatory biomarker derives from its dual nature: a decrease in lymphocyte counts, coupled with an elevation in neutrophil numbers underscores its effectiveness in gauging inflammatory status.²⁰

Neutrophils are quick to respond to inflammatory triggers, leading to an increase in their numbers within the bloodstream. Research indicates that individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) exhibit heightened levels of activation markers, such as CD11b/CD18, on both monocytes and neutrophils. This heightened expression results in greater adherence of neutrophils to the endothelial lining of blood vessels, a process that occurs independently of fasting glucose concentrations.²¹ In diabetic patients, leukocytes may also be activated by substances like leptin and advanced glycation end products. Once activated, these leukocytes contribute to systemic inflammation and damage to the endothelium through the release of reactive oxygen species from neutrophils, along with various cytokines.²² Moreover, there is a noted decrease in the ratio of regulatory T cells to helper T cells among those with diabetes. Increased levels of interleukins during inflammatory responses can lead to lymphopenia—reduction of lymphocytes—and neutrophilia, resulting in a significantly elevated Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR). This high NLR is linked to both microvascular and macrovascular complications associated with diabetes, as well as general metabolic dysfunction.²³ The current research indicates a significant association between elevated blood sugar levels and increased neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR). Our findings suggest that NLR can serve as both an indicator of varying degrees of glycemic control and a potential predictor for future complications in diabetic patients with poor glycemic management. Therefore, NLR is not merely an inflammatory marker; it may also play a direct role in the development of cardiovascular diseases among individuals with diabetes.

CONCLUSION:

NLR is significantly associated with poor glycemic control in diabetic patients. So NLR can be used as an alternative tool for diabetes monitoring specially in facilities where there is lack of HbA1c testing.

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